

QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE FRACTOGRAPHY OF GRP STRESS
CORROSION FRACTURE

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ABSTRACT

Planar fracture surfaces produced by the propagation of stress corrosion cracks perpendicular to the fibre direction in aligned glass/polyester material have been examined in detail. Fibres' fracture markings can be used to estimate their failure stresses. These values compare well with crack tip stresses deduced from the applied stress intensity factor, and have been used to calculate stress relaxation energies and crack growth rates. There are no indications that fibre fracture initiates at pre-existing flaws and this is in agreement with published models of stress corrosion crack propagation. Matrix markings have been used together with fibre markings to determine local crack growth directions. The position of matrix polygonal markings in specimens made with a toughened resin gives support to a proposed mechanism of diffusion assisted crack growth.

INTRODUCTION

The fracture of composite materials is complex and analysis of the fracture surfaces produced is often difficult due to the wide range of failure micromechanisms and attendant surface topographies [1,2]. In the presence of an acidic environment, aligned glass reinforced composites can fail at low applied stresses by stress corrosion crack growth perpendicular to the fibre direction. The basis of this process is the chemical degradation of E-glass fibres which occurs when they are exposed to mineral acids. This type of crack growth produces planar fracture surfaces. Fibre failure occurs where the environment meets the reinforcement, i.e. coplanar with matrix fracture resulting in minimal pullout. A review of this mode of failure has been provided by Hogg and Hull [3].

Planar fracture surfaces are ideal subjects for detailed fractographic study. This paper describes the results of fractographic studies

made on aligned glass/polyester crack growth specimens which were used to determine the influence of applied stress and matrix material on crack velocity [4,5].

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Aligned glass/polyester material was produced by filament winding using a flat-plate mandrel. Equerove 2347 E-glass roving (Pilkington Brothers) was used with Crystic 272 polyester resin (Scott Bader) to produce a standard material. Other matrix systems were used including a toughened version of Crystic 272 made by adding 20% (by volume) NV 1080 (Scott Bader). The test technique employed is shown in Fig.1. A modified double cantilever beam specimen is subjected to static loading and exposed to 0.6N HCL. Failure occurred by the slow propagation of a single stress corrosion crack from the starter notch. Complete descriptions of this technique and results obtained have been published elsewhere [4,5].

Fig.1 Stress corrosion crack growth test rig.

RESULTS

The most striking feature of stress corrosion fracture surfaces in aligned grp is their planar nature. This can be seen in Fig.2 which shows a typical fracture surface produced by a crack growing at $1.6 \times 10^{-8} \text{ ms}^{-1}$ under an applied stress intensity of $4.8 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$. There are some changes in fracture plane, for example at A in Fig.2. It has been shown that the extent this fracture surface stepping varies with applied stress intensity [4] with no stepping at low stress intensities ($<4.0 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$). It is also evident from Fig.2 that there is little or no individual fibre pullout.

Fig.2 Fracture surface of stress corrosion crack produced by $K_I = 4.8 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$

Fibre Fracture

Fibre fracture surfaces show the classic mirror, mist and hackle regions that have been described many times for glass fracture [6-8]. Two examples are shown in Fig.3. Fracture initiates at the focus of the mirror zone (A, Fig.3(a)) radiates to the mist zone (B) and bifurcates producing the hackle region (C) and a wedge of glass [6,8]. Bifurcation is seen more clearly in Fig.3(c) which shows a polished section perpendicular to the fracture plane. Thus the direction of crack propagation can be deduced from the fibre fracture markings and is arrowed in Fig.3(b).

Fig.3 Fibre fracture surfaces, (a) $K_I = 5.8 \text{ MNm}^{3/2}$
(b) $K_I = 4.1 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$ (c) Polished section

Many workers have analysed these fracture markings. An empirical relationship [6], has been deduced relating the mirror zone radius, M_r , to the fracture stress σ_f^* , i.e.

$$\sigma_f^* M_r^{1/2} = \text{constant.} \quad (1)$$

The value of the constant has been measured as $1.47 \text{ MNm}^{-3/2}$ for the type of fibres used in this work [7]. For the fibres shown in Fig.3(a) and (b) the failure stresses calculated in this way are 656 MNm^{-2} and 465 MNm^{-2} respectively. Where fracture has nucleated at a pre-existing flaw or notch, several workers have reported a fixed ratio between the flaw size and mirror zone radius [6,8]. This ratio is a simple function of the materials fracture toughness and the applied stress necessary to cause crack growth from the flaw. For rod shaped specimens the ratio is about 10:1 [8]. Thus for the fibres shown in Fig.3(a) and (b) flaw sizes of 1.0 and $0.5\mu\text{m}$ can be predicted, however close examination of the fibres mirror zones shows no sign of flaws.

Matrix Fracture

Two main forms of matrix marking were observed, river lines emanating from the fibres hackle markings and 'polygonal' lines forming a network around the fibres. Examples are labelled C and D respectively in Fig.2.

The river lines show that matrix fracture proceeds directly from fibre fracture and the polygonal lines are formed where matrix cracks growing from adjacent fibres meet. Any variation in fracture plane between neighbouring fibres will produce a step where the relevant matrix cracks meet and this marking will be accentuated by any plastic deformation or necking of the resin web as it fails.

Polished sections taken perpendicular to the fracture surfaces before separation of the two specimen halves reveal the extent of plastic deformation at the crack tip. One section is shown in Fig.4 where there are two matrix cracks from adjacent fibres meeting at point A. The crack tips are sharp, with a radius much less than $0.5\mu\text{m}$.

Fig.4 Polished section normal to fracture plane showing matrix cracks

Post Failure Surface Damage

After fracture, the surfaces are freely exposed to the environment, and degradation of the exposed fibres occurs. This is caused by leaching of metallic elements [9] resulting in fibre shrinkage, fracture, and eventual loss of the fibre ends as can be seen in Fig.5.

Fig.5 Post failure fracture surface damage

Post failure damage does indirectly give an indication of the condition of the interface region during crack propagation. Fig.6 shows sections perpendicular to fracture surfaces which have suffered acid attack. The fibre ends adjacent to the crack plane appear darker than the rest of the fibre and this is due to a change in composition of the glass caused by acid attack. The darkened region in Fig.6(b) extends down the sides of the fibre, implying that the environment has attacked the fibre's sides as well as the fractured end, whereas only the end of the fibre in Fig.6(a) has undergone changes. Fibres nearest to the tip of a stress corrosion crack (which had had least post failure exposure) had the type of profile shown in Fig.6(a) whilst those further from the crack tip showed evidence of side attack (Fig.6(b)). These profiles imply that the interface remains intact during the primary stress corrosion crack growth, and only fails after extreme post failure attack.

Fig.6 Polished sections normal to fracture plane showing fibre degradation

DISCUSSION

Using the empirical relationship (eqn.1) fibre failure stress can be calculated from mirror zone radius. It is interesting to compare stresses calculated in this way with the load applied to the specimen. The specimen geometry used was calibrated using a compliance technique so that K_I could be calculated from the applied load and crack length [4,5]. It is difficult to calculate the crack tip stress field for inhomogeneous anisotropic materials, however relationships between the principle stresses and K_I factor have been published for orthotropic homogeneous materials [10]. If this solution is used then stress parallel to the fibre axis, σ_y , can be calculated and this has been carried out [11] yielding the following result:

$$\sigma_y = \frac{K_I}{(2\pi r)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (2)$$

where r is the distance from the crack tip. In order to compare σ_y with the fibre failure stress calculated from M_r it is necessary to assume a value for r . Alternatively the variation in M_r may be compared directly with the variation in K_I , since from equations 1 and 2:-

$$\frac{K_I}{(2\pi r)^{\frac{1}{2}}} = \frac{1.47}{M_r^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad \text{i.e. } K_I \propto \frac{1}{M_r^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (3)$$

The variation of $1/M_r^{\frac{1}{2}}$ with K_I is shown in Fig.7. There are large variations in M_r from fibre to fibre over any area of fracture surface and so average values of M_r have been used. In each case about 50 fibre mirror zones were measured. There appears to be a linear variation of K_I with $(1/M_r^{\frac{1}{2}})$, which is in agreement with equation 3. The gradient of this line gives a value of 'r' at which the axial stress calculated from mirror zone radii is equal to the crack tip stress calculated from K_I using equation 2. The distance 'r' deduced in this way is 14.0 μ m which is of the same order of magnitude as the fibre diameter, d_f . Several authors have used d_f or $d_f/2$ when calculating the stress on the fibre at a crack tip from the applied stress intensity [11].

Fig.7 Variation of K_I with $1/M_r^{1/2}$

Fibre failure stress can be used to model the crack velocity, since the rate controlling step in this mode of stress corrosion cracking is fibre failure and matrix fracture between fibres is assumed to be spontaneous [3,5]. Some static fatigue results for fibres exposed to mineral acid have been published [12], and these may be used to calculate the time for fibre fracture if the applied load is known. Thus using failure stress (deduced from M_r) and published static fatigue data the time taken for the crack to advance from one fibre to the next may be estimated. If the materials volume fraction is known the overall crack velocity can be calculated. Calculated crack velocities are lower than measured values however the static fatigue data relate to bare, uniformly stressed fibres exposed to the environment whereas at the tip of a stress corrosion crack environmental attack is localised and the fibres axial stress will be a maximum at this point. For the fibres shown in Fig.3(a) and (b) the calculated failure times are 20×10^3 and 8×10^3 s which give crack velocities of 0.9 and $2.4 \times 10^{-9} \text{ ms}^{-1}$ respectively. These compare with measured growth rates of 4.0 and $8.0 \times 10^{-9} \text{ ms}^{-1}$.

Many attempts have been made to calculate the work of fracture by summing energies associated with the various microfracture processes. Matrix cleavage energy is often calculated using the fracture energy measured for bulk resin tests, which assumes that the resin fractures in the same way in a composite as it does in bulk form. Estimates of the crack tip plastic zone radius for Crystic 272 vary from 2 to $16 \mu\text{m}$, however zones of this size cannot be developed in resin webs that are much

smaller. Sections taken perpendicular to the fracture plane (Fig.4) show only small matrix crack tip radii with little plastic deformation. Any summation of fracture energies must take into account this variation between bulk fracture and crack propagation in the matrix of a high volume fraction composite.

Another energy absorbing microfracture process is fibre stress relaxation, i.e. the irrecoverable loss of strain energy from a fibre when it breaks. In order to calculate this energy the fibres failure stress is required and values deduced from mirror zone measurements can be used. This has been carried out and the energy levels obtained used in summations of the total fracture energy [11]. Agreement between calculated fracture energies and values deduced from applied crack driving forces is not good, however this is true of many similar attempts for composite materials.

As shown above it is possible to calculate the size of the initial flaw on the surface of the fibre assuming fracture started from such a flaw. There were no signs of such flaws, indicating that fracture does not initiate from pre-existing flaws but simply where the matrix crack meets the fibre. Lhymn and Schultz [13] proposed that an etch pit is formed on the fibre at this point, acting as a stress raiser which then leads to fracture. It seems likely that such an etch pit must grow to the dimensions of the flaw sizes calculated above before failure occurs, and should thus be visible at the focus of the mirror zone. This is not the case, however further consideration of fibre fracture nucleation and relevant fractographic study may aid explanation of this point.

An understanding of fibre and matrix markings enables the local crack growth directions and failure sequences to be deduced (Fig.2). The position matrix polygonal lines on some fracture surfaces gives direct support for a process of crack propagation dependent on diffusion of the environment [5]. With brittle matrices it is assumed that following fibre failure the web of resin surrounding the fibre fails up to the next intact fibre, allowing direct access of the environment to that fibre [3]. It has been suggested that with toughened resins matrix fracture arrests before reaching the next intact fibre, leaving it shielded from the environment by the resin [3,5]. The environment then has to diffuse through the matrix to reach the intact fibre.

The fracture surface of a specimen with a toughened matrix is shown in Fig.8. The polygonal line B-B marks the point at which the matrix crack growing from fibre A has arrested before reaching fibre C. Following failure of fibre C the surrounding matrix fails as arrowed. Thus it is the position of the polygonal line tangential to the fibres mirror zone that indicates whether environmental access is direct, or indirect by diffusion through a resin web. In Fig.2 (brittle matrix) the polygonal lines adjacent to the fibres mirror zones intersect with the fibres (e.g. at point B-B) showing complete failure of the matrix web up to the next intact fibre.

Fig.8 Signs of incomplete matrix web fracture in a ductile matrix

CONCLUSIONS

1. Fibre failure stresses deduced from mirror zone radii are in line with values derived from applied stress intensities. Crack velocities calculated using these failure stresses and static fatigue data show some agreement with measured values.
2. Fibre fracture does not appear to initiate at pre-existing crack like flaws.
3. Matrix markings on specimens made with a toughened resin support a process of diffusion assisted crack propagation.
4. Polished sections perpendicular to the crack plan show no sign of plastic deformation at matrix crack tips and indicate that the interface remains intact during crack propagation.

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